

MODELLING DAMAGE DUE TO LOW SPEED IMPACT IN LAMINATED COMPOSITES OF TOUGHENED INTERFACES THROUGH 'EX SITU' TECHNIQUE

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Keywords: 'Ex-situ' toughening; Delamination; Cohesive elements.

ABSTRACT

Laminated composites are widely employed in the aerospace industry for their high performances. One of the major drawbacks in using these materials for aerospace applications has been their weaknesses in resisting lateral impacts which tend to induce damage in laminates. Delamination is one of the major forms of damage which compromise the integrity of the laminates as load carrying structures. To tackle this issue, the 'ex-situ' toughening technique, was developed by Yi et al [1,3] in Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials (BIAM), China and has since been applied successfully to processing laminated composites made from prepregs and later to those made using RTM. Experimental evidences have demonstrated the toughening effects of such technique. Effects of toughening are reflected mainly through critical energy release rates for mode I and II, G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} , which to a large extent dictate the impact damage resistance of the laminates. These properties were obtained through standard tests, namely, double cantilever beam (DCB) and end-notched flexure (ENF) delamination tests for mode I and II, respectively. Three types of laminates made through RTM were used, neat BMI (non-toughened) as the control and 'ex-situ' RTM-16.8% and 20.2% PAEK, respectively, in the experiments conducted by BIAM. This paper is to present the capability of theoretical modelling the delamination damage of 'ex-situ' toughened laminates due to lateral impact using finite elements with appropriate treatments. Models representing the DCB and ENF specimens were generated to reproduce the results of these tests, and the predicted critical energy release rates is shown to agree well with the input values. The numerical modelling for these cases facilitated the development of FE model simulating the standard mixed mode tests, the prediction for which are also given in the paper.

1. INTRODUCTION

The modern fibre reinforced composites have been successfully used in aerospace engineering applications, with most notable examples being Boeing 787 and Airbus A350. One of the most common types of composites are laminated composites. One of the major drawbacks of laminated composites has been their weaknesses in resisting lateral impacts which tend to induce delamination in the laminates. Delamination is one of the major forms of damage which compromise the integrity of damaged laminates as load carrying structures. Various techniques have been attempted to improve the impact resistance of laminated composites. The present article deals with the effects of a promising approach, the 'ex-situ' toughening technique, developed by BIAM, China [1-4]. Experimental evidences have demonstrated the toughening effects of such technique. In this paper, the effects of toughening on the performance of material are investigated numerically, via FE modelling.

The 'ex-situ' toughening technique under consideration was proposed by Yi et al [1-6]. It has been successfully applied for manufacturing laminated composites based on prepregs, and later when making composites with resin transfer moulding (RTM) process [5-9]. The experimental data measured in standard tests as reported in [6-9] were used to validate modelling in this paper.

The effects of toughening are reflected mainly through two characteristic mechanical properties, critical energy release rates for mode I and II, G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} . These properties have been published in [7] which were obtained through standard tests according to [10,11]. The standard test for mode I used specimens in form of a double cantilever beam (DCB) and those for mode II were end-notched flexure (ENF).

As a first attempt of addressing the theoretical modelling of the impact behaviour of laminated composites of this kind, in which delamination features the damage, it makes sense to start from some relatively simple cases to build up the confidence on theoretical modelling. The cases selected for this purpose were those standard tests for mode I and II, respectively. After demonstrated an established capability of modelling delamination damage, standard mixed mode cases are then able to be numerically simulated. The objective is to demonstrate the modelling capability for generic problem of delaminations while the immediate outcomes can serve as a means of virtual testing which is of practical value as mode fix ratio cannot be exhausted and pure experimental way of data acquisition can be costly and time consuming.

2. COMPOSITE SPECIMENS AND TESTING CASES

The details of the experimental set-ups and specifications of composite specimens are reported in [7]. The composite was manufactured through an RTM process at the National Key Laboratory of Advanced Composites. Commercial G827 carbon cloth (T300-3k, 160g/m², Hexcel) was used as a reinforcement, which was injected with bismaleimide (BMI) resin under a trade-name of 6421 produced. The ‘ex situ’ toughening was introduced by coating the carbon cloth with a controlled amount of Polyaryletherketone(PEAK) [7] the usage of which was expressed in terms of weight percentage (wt%) in the composite.. Once the composite is injected with the resin and cured, the toughening agent melts and this creates toughened resin areas between the plies as schematically shown in fig. 1.

Figure 1: Schematics of the toughening mechanism [6]

Three types of specimens are used, neat BMI (non-toughened) as the control, ‘ex situ’ RTM-16.8%PAEK and ‘ex-situ’ RTM-20.2%PAEK. The dimensions of the specimens in DCB, ENF and MMB tests are specified in the sketches as shown in Figs. 2, 3 and 4, respectively.

Figure 2: The DCB specimen for mode I tests [10]

Figure 3: The ENF specimen for mode II tests [11]

Figure 4: The DCB specimen for MMB test

3. MATERIAL MODELS AND PROPERTIES

The FE models for all these cases were generated in Abaqus software. The constitutive behaviour of plies and interface was prescribed via the Abaqus “built-in” material models [15]. Composite plies with unidirectional carbon fibre reinforcement were defined as transversely isotropic elastic material. Continuum shell elements were applied to mesh the composite plies, while the interface between plies was defined via the cohesive elements.

The elastic behaviour of the interface is defined in terms of tractions and separation relationship expressed in local coordinate system for the cohesive element concerned as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} t_n \\ t_s \\ t_t \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{T} \begin{bmatrix} K_{nn} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & K_{ss} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & K_{tt} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta_n \\ \delta_s \\ \delta_t \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where T is the thickness of the cohesive element and K_{nn} , K_{ss} and K_{tt} represent the stiffness characteristics of the interface in normal and two perpendicular tangential directions to the interface. The interface stiffnesses are necessary input data for the FE model in order to define the properties of the cohesive elements. In this sense, the selection of these stiffnesses is not unique. A reasonable choice was suggested by Zou et al [16] as follows

$$K_i = (10^5 \sim 10^7) \times \tau_i^c \quad (2)$$

where $i=nn, ss$ and tt and τ_i^c are the corresponding strengths (direct and shear) which can usually be obtained directly from the matrix as delamination tends to take place at the interface where a resin-rich layer is usually present. The values of the strengths of the matrix τ_i^c employed in the present simulation have been listed in Table 1.

Damage initiation is governed by a quadratic interfacial traction criterion, which is defined as follows:

$$\left\{ \frac{\langle t_n \rangle}{t_n^c} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{\langle t_s \rangle}{t_s^c} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{\langle t_t \rangle}{t_t^c} \right\}^2 = 1 \quad (3)$$

where t_n^c , t_s^c and t_i^c are the interfacial strengths under pure modes, and pointed brackets around t_n mean that only a positive value counts.

The interfacial traction and separation relationship as given in (1) governs the behaviour of the interface up to the point of damage initiation. Once damage initiates, the damage evolution law will govern the behaviour of the interface in terms of the degradation of the interface stiffness. A non-dimensional scalar damage variable D , which defined in linear softening scheme is

$$D = \frac{\delta_m^f (\delta_m^{max} - \delta_m^0)}{\delta_m^{max} (\delta_m^f - \delta_m^0)} \quad (4)$$

Where $\delta_m^f = 2G^C / T_{eff}^0$ with T_{eff}^0 as the effective traction at damage initiation. δ_m^f refers to the maximum value of the effective displacement attained during the loading history. $D=0$ represents the undamaged state and $D=1$ a fully delaminated state. An evolution law based on fracture mechanics can be applied to predict the propagation of the damage. A power law criterion for mixed mode delamination is employed

$$\left\{ \frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}} \right\}^\alpha + \left\{ \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}} \right\}^\beta + \left\{ \frac{G_{III}}{G_{IIIc}} \right\}^\gamma = 1 \quad (5)$$

where G_I , G_{II} and G_{III} represent the energy release rates for each of three individual modes and G_{Ic} , G_{IIc} and G_{IIIc} are their critical values. $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$ and $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 2$ are most commonly used.

The relevant mechanical properties for composite plies and interface layers are summarised in Table 1. It should be reasonable to assume that the interlaminar tensile strength of the toughened specimens takes the same value as that of the resin in its untoughened state and the critical energy release rate for mode III takes the same value of that of mode II. Even so, the properties as provided in [7-9] are still insufficient in order to carry out a complete analysis. To facilitate the modelling, the remaining properties as listed in Table 2 as required have been obtained based on the similar constituents, T300 carbon fibres and a common epoxy resin system as shown in [12], where use has been made of the micromechanical composite characterisation tool, UnitCells©, developed at University of Nottingham [13,14]. However, at the fibre volume fraction of 54.3% for the untoughened specimen as given in [8], the longitudinal Young's modulus would be significantly high than 102 GPa as provided in [8]. It was suspected that the specimens were made from UD fabrics where a small percentage of fibres were used as the binders. To match the effective longitudinal Young's modulus reasonably, a fibre volume fraction of 45% was assumed as the fibres aligned in the longitudinal direction. As the properties obtained in this way are relatively of secondary significances in the present analysis, their absolute values are not expected to cause much error.

Finally, the values of longitudinal tensile elastic modulus as specified in Table 1 for all three toughening cases were used to define the longitudinal tensile modulus of the ply.

Mechanical properties	Surface-loading level with PAEK		
	0.0	16.8wt%	20.2wt%
Longitudinal tensile modulus E_1 (GPa)	102	105	112
Longitudinal compressive modulus E_1 (GPa)	101	104	110
Longitudinal Flexural modulus E_1 (GPa)	108	115	113
Longitudinal Poisson ratio ν_{12}	0.32	0.3	0.34
Interlaminar tensile strength σ^f (MPa)	67.6	67.6	67.6
Interlaminar shear strength τ^f (MPa)	103	108	104
G_{Ic} (J/m ²)	215	453	627
$G_{IIc} = G_{IIIc}$ (J/m ²)	510	971	905

Table 1: Mechanical properties available from [7-9]

Engineering Constant	Identification
Transverse modulus $E_2=E_3$ (GPa)	4.8
Transverse Poisson ratio ν_{23}	0.42
Longitudinal shear modulus $G_{12}=G_{13}$ (GPa)	2.0
Transverse shear modulus (GPa)	1.7

Table 2: Mechanical properties supplemented to facilitate the modelling

4. Results on delamination modelling

4.1 A double cantilever beam under mode I loading condition

A FE model of DCB under symmetric loading was generated to simulate a pure mode I delamination scenario. The overall dimensions of the FE model are specified in Fig. 2. An interface was modelled by a layer of cohesive elements placed along the mid-surface of the beam. The initial delamination is represented by the 45 mm long segment where no interface between the upper and lower halves of the beam is defined. In the test samples, an initial delamination was introduced by inserting a thin PTFE film in the mid-plane of the beam, and this corresponded to 25 mm initial delamination length in the model. However, according to the DCB delamination test procedure [10], the initial delamination has to be propagated by at least 20mm in a pre-loading phase. To account for this in the FE model, initial delamination length was extended to 45mm, with effective delamination length being measured as a distance between the loading hinge and the delamination front

A mesh sensitivity study was undertaken to determine an appropriate mesh size. This study revealed that in order to capture delamination growth reasonably, the mesh around the delamination front is to be sufficiently fine.

Previous studies of delamination behaviour indicate that for a general mixed mode case, a number of layers of continuum shell elements are required for the sublaminates on either side of the delamination [17]. As a compromise between the accuracy of predictions and the computational costs, for this particular case, two layers of continuum shell elements were defined on each side of interface layer. The in-plane mesh of the upper and lower halves of composite beam matched the in-plane mesh of the cohesive layer.

The mesh employed in the present simulation shown in fig.5 has been verified as a converged mesh in the sense that further refinement would not result in noticeable improvement in the accuracy of the results.

Figure 5: The mesh employed for modelling the DCB
(a) Top view and (b) Deformed, (c) Crack front zoom-in

Due to the symmetry of the problem, only half of width of the DCB was be modelled with appropriate symmetry conditions imposed to the nodes on the symmetry plane.

All nodes on the tip of each DCB leg are connected to a reference node through a kinematic coupling offered in Abaqus [15]. A reference node is located at the centre of the end surface of each leg, each of which has six degrees of freedom (DOF). For these two reference nodes, the side way displacement and rotations about the axis of the DCB and that normal to the plane of the DCB are constrained because of the symmetry of the structure and the same effects can be achieved by imposing the symmetry condition to these two reference nodes. The DOF of the reference nodes representing the transverse displacement, i.e. deflection, will be prescribed a designated displacement as the mechanism of loading in a displacement controlled manner. The reactions can be obtained at these DOFs of the two reference nodes as the load applied. Prescribing the opposite displacements at these two reference nodes leads to the opening mode of the DCB. The remaining DOFs of the reference nodes are left free. The rigid body displacement along the axis of the DCB is constrained at the far end where the deflection and the rotation are also constrained to ensure the symmetric behaviour of the two sublaminates on either side of the delamination, as is often imposed in the experiments.

From the results of the simulation, load-displacement curve can be obtained from the reference nodes directly. To account for the absolute delamination opening displacement, the difference of the two displacements (one positive and one negative) needs to be used to comply with the conventional sense of the displacement in this context. Also, since only half of the DCB has been modelled due to the symmetry, to recover the case for the full DCB, the load needs to be doubled.

A set of three such load-displacement curves are shown in Fig. 6 corresponding to the three types of the specimens as specified in [7] with different extent of ‘ex situ’ toughened interfaces. The experimental results are also included in Fig. 6 for comparison. As the delamination lengths are unavailable for the experimental data, meaningful comparisons can only be made for two pieces of information, the delamination propagation part of the load displacement curves and the critical energy release rate worked out from the simulation results according to the formula given in Standard HB7402-96.

The initial linear part of the load-displacement curve cannot be compared directly as the slope varies with the initial delamination length. In the current models, this is 45mm, which is the effective delamination length as called in the standard [10]. The slopes of the linear sections in all three cases agree well with the mechanics of materials calculation assuming the delaminated part as cantilever beams. However, this delamination length was not available from the experimental data. The delamination lengths were unlikely to be the same as in the current modelling. However, the initial delamination lengths should not affect the propagation part of the load-displacement curve, where the critical energy release rate should be derived primarily according to the standard [10]. The comparisons for this part should be meaningful. Reasonable agreements can be found for all three cases, untoughened (the control) and toughened with 16.8wt% and 20.2wt% PEAK, respectively.

Also included in Fig. 6 are the delamination lengths from the simulation of these cases as functions of delamination opening displacement. No experimental data were available for direct comparison. The reason for having the load-displacement curves and the delamination length-displacement curves included in the same graph is that one requires in the data in order to work out the critical energy release rate according to the standard [10].

In the first and the third cases, the predicted load-displacement curves show clear bends at a delamination length of about 90mm. The abrupt changes were because delamination had propagated to an area where the mesh was no longer fine enough. One does not really need any data from there in order to work out the critical energy release rate. The second case was therefore interrupted before reaching that point.

Figure 6: The load-displacement and delamination length-displacement curves for mode 1 loading (a) Untoughened (b) 16.8% wt PAEK toughened (c) 20.2% wt PAEK toughened

The critical energy release rates for the three specimens concerned obtained from the present simulations according to the standard [10] are listed in Table 3 and compared with experimentally measured values which have been used as the input data to facilitate the present simulation. Good agreements are observed as expected. This serves as a reasonable verification of the simulations conducted to the level of accuracy as shown.

Extent of toughening		Experimental	Present simulation
0.0	[J/m ²]	215	229
16.8wt%	[J/m ²]	453	463
20.2wt%	[J/m ²]	627	642

Table 3: Mode I critical energy release rate

Minor discrepancies in the predicted critical energy release rates are attributed to the following reasons.

- 1) Experimental variability as a common observation for composites;
- 2) Assumed missing material properties listed in Table 2;
- 3) As a part of the cohesive element, a very small amount of viscosity has to be introduced to stabilise the numerical iterations which tends to dissipate a small amount of energy.
- 4) The curved appearance of the delamination front suggests that there is a minor tendency of the delamination propagating sideways. This would be an interesting point for discussion as it touches upon a fundamental question. The propagation of delamination along the direction of fibres is the desired manner as also assumed in the standards [10,18]. However, there is no reason to believe that the propagation in the sideways direction, i.e. transverse to the fibres, would share the same critical energy release rate with the propagation in the direction along the fibres.

Delamination shape in mode I loading has a curved front as shown in fig7. Due to the model used is only a half, the whole shape is reasonably similar to observation in reality experiment. This thumbnail shape for delamination front can be expected by anticlastic effects caused by free edge effect. The damage is tend to proceed in the middle of the interface and spread outwards to the both edges.

Figure 7: Movement of delamination shape at crack front

4.2 End notched flexure (ENF) for mode II

The second problem is an end notched flexure (ENF) test to produce a pure mode II scenario. Another FE model was constructed to simulate the standard test for measuring the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness. The ENF specimen is dimensioned as shown in Fig. 3. The same considerations as in those described in the subsection above have been given to this case as well. The mesh employed shown in fig8 in ENF simulation was similar to that in DCB case. A major difference from the DCB problem is the introduction of a contact condition between the two sides of the notch to prevent interpenetration of each other during the deformation process as the two sublaminates tend to deflect towards the same direction.

Figure 8: The mesh employed for modelling the ENF
 (a) Top view and (b) Deformed, (c) Crack front zoom-in

The ENF specimen is constrained as a simply supported beam and this was duly reflected in the FE model. The vertical displacement degree of freedom of the row of nodes along the loading line is constrained to that of a reference node through equation constraints [14]. The reference node is fully constrained except the degree of freedom in the loading direction. The load is applied in a displacement controlled mode by prescribing the displacements of the reference point.

The obtained load-displacement curves are shown in Fig. 9 corresponding to the three types of the specimens tested by BIAM as shown in [7] with different extent of ‘ex situ’ toughened interfaces. The experimental results are also included in Fig. 9 for comparison, although the original experimental data, shown as solid lines in purple, appeared erroneous apparently as elaborated. It was believed that the experimental data misrecorded the displacement by a factor of 10 for the untoughened case and 20 for both toughened case, as shown in double dot chain in purple. The purpose of scaling here is not to draw direct comparisons between the simulations and experiments but to show the full curves in the same graphs. It can be observed, nevertheless, reasonable agreements are found in the peak loads between corresponding theoretical and experimental results.

The delamination length versus displacement curves are also shown in Fig. 9. It is clear that delamination tends to propagate rapidly after the load peaks, accompanied by a sharp drop in load. A steady behaviour re-establishes afterward. This is a typical mode II behaviour which needs to be paid due attention to in future simulations of mixed mode cases and panel impact cases.

Figure 9: The load-displacement and delamination length-displacement curves for the ENF(a) untoughened (b) 16.8% wt PAEK toughened (c) 20.2% wt PAEK toughened

Similarly, the critical energy release rates have been obtained from the simulation data according to the standard. They are shown in Table 4. They tend to reproduce the input data reasonably accurately. The modelling approach as will be followed in the subsequent part of the project has been verified to this level of accuracy. The analysis on the discrepancy in the previous problem and the discussion made there apply largely to the present problem, except that the delamination front in mode II is no longer as curved as in mode I.

Extent of toughening		Experimental	Present simulation
0.0	[J/m ²]	510	491
16.8wt%	[J/m ²]	971	912
20.2wt%	[J/m ²]	905	852

Table 4: Mode II critical energy release rate

4.3 Mesh sensitivity studies

In the utilization of finite element analysis, mesh sensitivity always has uncertain influence to the model calibration. Parametric mesh sensitivity has been made in mode I and mode II simulation. The refinement mesh can be various sensitivity in different cases. The Fig10 shows the mesh sensitivity along length of the model, while fine mesh in width is not strictly required to enhance the model. The legends below indicate the length of each interface element.

Figure 10: Load-displacement curves on mesh sensitive studies in mode I loading
(a) Untoughened (b) 16.8% wt PAEK toughened

Figure 11: Stress contour plot of interface elements in Mode II loading
(a) 52 elements along width (b) 55 elements along the width

Inversely, the mesh in width is more sensitive in the mode II loading. The results can be affected enormously with tiny different parameters. The “ragged” delamination front is clearly observed in Fig. 11(a), while adding 3 more elements to refine the mesh can overcome the convergence difficulty in this case.

4.4 Simulation for Mix-mode

Pure prediction ability found in mode I and mode II has been demonstrated to present simulation for mix-mode. The finite element analytical model is in demission criterion form the standard [19]. Due to

the inconstant mesh sensitivity in mode I and mode II. Compatible mesh is utilized to optimise mix mode test. Unlikely to build the displacement correlation of mode I hinged and mode II roller, an extra rigid lever with two attached corresponding reference nodes is placed above the beam as shown in Fig12.

Figure 12: Mix mode deformed model

Although static force distribution can be derived from beam theory to prescribe the load boundary condition, the non-linear geometric displacement burden the uncertainty occurring in the transformation calculation of lever end point which is the only comparable numerical point between simulation and experiment. Various G_{II}/G ratios results can be simulated by adjust the lever length 'c'. Some displacement and force curves of simulation results are in Figure 13.

Figure 13: The load-displacement curves for mix mode related to different mode ratios (a) Untoughened (b) 16.8%PAEK toughened (c) 20.2%PAEK toughened

With the dominated contribution of G_I , the curves are more closed trend as mode I. Also, the forces are in decrement due to the high requirement in mode II failure. Currently, experiments are in progress in BIAM. Subsequent comparison will able to continue as long as the experimental results are presented.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The financial support to the work presented in this paper from Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials, Beijing, China, through Grant No. RGS107903 is gratefully acknowledged. The authors are also grateful for access to the University of Nottingham High Performance Computing Facility.

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